

ANALYSIS OF THE QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES PROVIDING TRANSPORT AND TECHNICAL SERVICES

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Abstract: In this article, transport and technical service is composed of many specializations in enterprise management: service management, financial management, administrative management, content structure, product quality assessment and quality level assessment to improve it. about the author's detailed thoughts and opinions are kept and stated.

Key words: Management, composition, structure, transport, technique, finance, specialization

Of course, the activity of the enterprise is a complex system and there are activities of various forms, among them are organizational-management, engineering-managerial, accounting economy, control-auditing, research, project-research and other types of activities. Finding a solution to economic issues largely depends on the level of economic efficiency of industrial enterprises. It serves as a basis for changing production techniques and technologies, improving material incentives for employees, and paying taxes and mandatory payments to the state budget in order to increase the economic efficiency of enterprises. Profitability of the enterprise is crucial for its operation in the conditions of the market economy, especially in the competitive environment. The development of mechanical engineering in Uzbekistan is a prominent economic issue. Among the companies that are starting production today are "Navoi-Motors" LLC, "Manas Auto-Sanoat" LLC, "Namangan Changan Motors" LLC, "ADM Jizzakh" LLC, "Auto Motors

Asia" LLC, "Abbos-Eco Agro" LLC, "Hyundai Motor Uz Namangan" LLC is planning to launch the production of passenger cars, pickups, trucks, minibuses and other vehicles. It is impossible to develop without the organization of comprehensive services for the sale and servicing of cars, as well as the development of the car economy. At the moment, specialized stations for the sale of cars and their technical service are operating in the center of all regions. In order to provide them with modern equipment and diagnostic tools, the issues of accreditation and network development by metrologists are important. To evaluate the quality of the product and to improve it, it is necessary to evaluate the quality level. The assessment of the product quality level serves as a basis for the implementation of the necessary management effects in the product quality system. Quality is a set of specifications that indicate the ability of a product or service to meet specified requirements or expected needs. The precision achieved with the help of qualified personnel and the appropriate technology, as well as the efficiency of production and production, lead to the satisfaction of consumer demand and quality. shows the secret and during its production, its appearance is perfect, company signs are clear, informational material and documents are complete, and packing and placing works are carried out so that the appearance of the product is not damaged. indicates a good level of implementation.

In order to meet the two main requirements of modern industry - time and quality, the main attention is paid to the development of

reliable transition mechanisms for measuring industrial products on coordinate measuring machines. Sales of vehicles under the Chevrolet trademark, which are widely distributed in our country, have increased dramatically since March of last year. In 2023, sales of branded cars in this country will increase by 190%. Due to this, the quality of cars produced in our country is rising to the world level.

Great attention is paid to the quality and competitiveness of the products produced in our republic. In this direction, various laws and regulations are being adopted and implemented. One such law is the "Evaluation of Conformity" of the Republic of Uzbekistan on" law. This law was developed on the basis of international conformity assessment systems and laws in countries with high quality infrastructure and deep analysis, and the coming into force of this law serves as another confirmation of the attention paid to product quality and safety in our Republic.

The quality of the service provided in the car maintenance enterprise is defined: the quality of work performed on car maintenance and equipment; the culture of customer service and the level of its organization. It is necessary to satisfy the demand for service in the organization of the management of the production process in the car maintenance enterprise, to spend less time and achieve high quality in the use of funds and assets in the car maintenance and quick management of processes. Management system in transport and technical service enterprises: Transport and technical service enterprise management is a major specialty, consisting of many specialties: service management, financial management, administrative management. Of course, enterprise activity is a

complex system. and is an activity of various forms: organizational-management, engineering-managerial, accounting, economic, control-auditing, research, design-research and other activities, made up of general questions. Organization of service processes to improve the service activities of the transport and technical service enterprise improvement, regulatory and technical support, rational use of technical means and introduction of regulatory documents in the required order are considered the main tasks of the enterprise manager. Twenty years ago, on July 19, 1996, the official opening ceremony of the joint venture "UzDEUavto" was held in Asaka. Our first president, Islam Karimov, said at the solemn ceremony: "Our country, as well as our far and near neighbors, understand very well that to build such a huge factory, it takes not only economic and financial capabilities, but also great spiritual strength. you need to have a heart" At the same time, the fact that our country, which is one of the 52 car-producing countries, ranks among the top thirty in terms of production capacity indicates that the international prestige of the national auto industry is increasing.

All this is a practical confirmation that the idea that Uzbekistan is a great country in the future, put forward by our President in the first days of our independence, is coming true. According to Uzavtosanoat joint-stock company, in the first quarter of this year, 55,000 cars, more than 1,100 ISUZU, 198 MAN trucks, 129,800 batteries, 30,000 aggregate and other products are produced. At the moment, the company is working regularly to further increase the volume of production, develop the economy and expand exports. Today, more than 250 dealers of the automobile industry of our country are operating in the CIS countries. Products have been exported to Russia, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Indonesia, Brazil, Turkey, Republic of Korea and other countries.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that during the research on this article, we learned to analyze the quality indicators in the transport and technical service enterprises. The place of standards and certificates was brought to the show enterprises. Also, a management system was introduced in transport and technical service enterprises. Scientifically based classification of them is of great importance for the correct organization of cost accounting in automobile transport enterprises.

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